

Assessing the Economic Impact of COVID-19

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The COVID-19 pandemic, a global health crisis, has had a severe impact on lives across the world. It has brought about a major shift in the economy, leaving behind significant issues that are and will continue to be addressed. Understanding the impact of COVID-19 on the economy is crucial due to the far-reaching consequences of the pandemic. The spread of the virus led to widespread lockdowns, causing innumerable economic challenges such as supply chain disruptions, food insecurity, unemployment, and increased poverty. This research demonstrates the effects on various groups and informs future preparedness and policy responses. It also addresses the unequal impact, particularly on vulnerable populations, contributing to discussions on the government's attempts to build a more resilient economic system. A question emerges when acknowledging the aftermath of the unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic: To what extent did COVID-19 affect society, and what lasting changes can be observed? The perspectives researched were the economic impact on vulnerable populations and the government's response, focusing on the effectiveness of new measures.

The economic impact of COVID-19 has hit vulnerable populations especially hard, worsening financial difficulties and widening existing disparities. Hai-Anh H Dang, an economist and researcher following international development, explains how “individuals in poorer quintiles residing in more economically unequal countries tend to offer even less government support” (Hai-Anh H et al., 2022). Economic inequality, COVID-19’s long-term structural changes in the economy amplify the disparities between government response and

individuals with disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds. Martin Mckee, a professor of European public health, highlights that many individuals worldwide “found themselves living from month to month, facing insecurity of ... food” (Mckee et al., 2020). The economic strain on supply chains resulted in a domino effect, leading to increased prices for various food items in local markets. This occurrence often hits vulnerable populations the hardest, causing issues of food accessibility and affordability. Such price hikes impact not only consumers but also small businesses and local producers who may struggle to adapt to the fluctuating market. Disruptions such as these are what caused immediate challenges as well as global shifts affecting prices, availability, and sustainability. A peer-reviewed article by Dr. Sian Reece, a scientist and economic researcher, explains that “[w]ith ever increasing cost of living, energy prices and inflation since the pandemic, the ability of families to recover from the effects of the pandemic is untenable without intervention” (Reece et al., 2023). Although there might have been some recovery in financial stability, many families continue to struggle with economic insecurities stemming from the pandemic, and these crisis factors are hindering a complete return to pre-pandemic financial security. Based on available evidence, this view compares to that of the government in terms of their response in that they support one another and are consistent through the identifiable issues regarding the economic impact of COVID-19.

Government responses to COVID-19's economic impact are crucial in shaping recovery, with policies and stimulus packages aimed at mitigating adverse effects and overall economic stability. United Nations News, providing reliable, impartial information from the private sector and non-governmental organizations, states that “exceptionally strong labor markets are,

however, making it harder for central banks to tame inflation” (United Nations News, 2023). This is contributing to an increased demand for goods and services, leading to rising prices and may hinder specific industries, affect consumer behavior, or influence government policies. Temporary policy changes made during the pandemic, such as unemployment insurance, food assistance, health, and housing programs, helped protect the economy and limit poverty, “but temporary measures can only have a limited impact on long-term challenges that mean that millions of people in the U.S. have difficulty affording the basics and lack health coverage” (CBPP., et al). This information from CBPP, a registered organization, shows that these short-term solutions, while beneficial in the immediate term, may not manage the underlying, persistent economic challenges faced by many. These temporary solutions can't solve long-term challenges like affording basics and lacking healthcare coverage. Sustainable and comprehensive approaches are needed to overcome these challenges beyond the immediate crisis. Addressing this issue, “policymakers made permanent what had been a temporary option to provide 12 months of postpartum health coverage through Medicaid” and “extended the American Rescue Plan’s expanded premium tax credits that made ACA marketplace coverage more affordable and helped lead to a significant increase in enrollment” (CBPP., et al). According to Aleksandra Kordonska, a researcher with a Ph.D. in economics and expertise in the international political economy, “governments have implemented an extraordinary range of new policy measures to tackle the health and economic consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic” (Kordonska et al., 2022). For example, the World Bank Group provided financial support of \$204 billion “directed to the poorest and the most vulnerable countries” (Kordonska et al., 2022). These actions highlight a shift toward longer-term solutions, but additional efforts are necessary to continue to

better the economic state of the world. Another peer-reviewed written by research professors such as Guanglv Huang says that “with the deep involvement of the government, highly egalitarian countries with high economic freedom are able to allocate resources fairly and quickly, thus affecting the speed of epidemic control” but, “[p]oor economic freedom and social inequality can make it take longer to control the COVID-19 pandemic or even perpetuate it” (Huang et al., 2022). So far, the government's quick responses and robust economic systems have allowed them to quickly distribute resources during the crisis, and the specific actions and policies that helped these nations respond effectively. The article explores the challenges that governments face in implementing timely health measures or providing support to populations negatively impacted by COVID-19 due to limited resources and regulatory constraints. Directors at PwC, a company that provides assurance, tax, and advisory services, explain that “for too long, governments and businesses have operated in silos, resulting in economies that are neither sustainable nor inclusive”, and this is unsustainable for future progress (Shannon et al., 2021). “Governments and businesses are facing a world that has been radically changed by COVID-19, and recovery will probably be marked by significant instability and change” (Shannon et al., 2021). Assessing these actions helps understand how governments have dealt with and are continuing to deal with this crisis, connecting to the potential long-term effects of these policy interventions and their effectiveness in stabilizing the economy. Connecting governments and businesses to build a sustainable and inclusive economy is important because collaboration is essential to developing policies and practices that promote economic growth while also ensuring sustainability.

The significance of examining the economic repercussions of COVID-19 provides a nuanced view of how the pandemic may shape societal and economic structures in the long term. This research helps gain a more informed understanding of the situation amidst the evolving information. Vulnerable populations have encountered challenges that intertwine with the efforts of the government. Both perspectives reveal how the aftermath of the pandemic requires adaptive strategies from governments and businesses to manage the fluctuating economy. It will be beneficial to capitalize on the current opportunity to implement initiatives that can lead to positive and lasting societal changes. The implications of this research extend to future actions. By leveraging these insights, society can work towards a more impartial, adaptive, and resilient economy.

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